

The in-depth reading and its enemies

Nilo Silvio Costa Serpa¹
Francisco Josmey Miranda²

Resumo: O presente artigo discute os potenciais prejuízos cognitivos da ausência de leitura profunda no cotidiano de jovens e adultos, abrindo uma reflexão sobre o que esperar de uma civilização digital acerca de como a espécie sobreviverá com as suas características mentais distintivas seriamente transformadas pela convivência com entidades algorítmicas. Enfatiza-se principalmente a perda das capacidades empáticas e de susceptibilidade a *insights*, e a perda da capacidade de definir objetivos concretos. O trabalho evidencia a necessidade de uma ampla revisão crítica dos fundamentos da educação, bem como das práticas pedagógicas e de seus atuais apensos tecnológicos, os quais têm constituído muito mais um fim do que um meio auxiliar para otimização de processos.

Palavras-chave: Leitura profunda. Cognição. Empatia.

Abstract: This article discusses the potential cognitive impairments resulting from the absence of in-depth reading in the daily lives of young people and adults, prompting reflection on what to expect from a digital civilization regarding how the species will survive with its distinctive mental characteristics seriously transformed by coexistence with algorithmic entities. It primarily emphasizes the loss of empathic abilities and susceptibility to insights, and the loss of the ability to define concrete goals. The work highlights the need for a broad critical review of the foundations of education, as well as the need for a restructuring of pedagogical practices

¹ Arquiteto Urbanista (Universidade Santa Úrsula - USU, Rio de Janeiro – RJ), *Master of Business Administration* (Fundação Getúlio Vargas - FGV, Rio de Janeiro – RJ), PhD em *Physique Théorique (Académie de Bordeaux, Bordeaux – FR)*, PhD em *Ingénierie de l'Environnement (Université des Sciences de l'Homme et de l'Environnement, Paris – FR)*, *Magister in Scientia* em Astronomia (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro - UFRJ), Livre Docente em Física Teórica (Centro Brasileiro de Pesquisas Físicas - CBPF, Rio de Janeiro – RJ), Neurocientista Cognitivo, Professor do Programa de Mestrado Profissional em Desenvolvimento e Periferias, Universidade Santa Úrsula - USU, Rio de Janeiro – RJ, Orcid 0000-0003-1041-6766, nilo.serpa@usu.edu.br.

² Bacharel em Economia (Universidade Regional do Cariri - URCA, CE), Licenciado em Matemática (Universidade Estadual do Ceará - UECE), Especialista em Metodologia do Ensino Fundamental e Médio (Universidade Vale do Acaraú - UVA, CE), Especialista em Gestão da Educação Pública (Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora - UFJF, MG), Professor Efetivo de Matemática nas redes estadual e municipal do Município de Brejo Santo – CE, Mestrando do Programa de Mestrado Profissional em Desenvolvimento e Periferias (Universidade Santa Úrsula - USU, Rio de Janeiro – RJ), francisco.miranda1391@souusu.com.br.

Recebido em: 12 /04/2026

Aprovado em: 22/05/2026

Sistema de Avaliação: *Double Blind Review*

and their current technological appendages, which have become more of an end in themselves than a means to optimize processes.

Keywords: Deep reading. Cognition. Empathy.

PROLOG

A long time ago, when I was very young and well before going into physics, I began my studies in anthropology with Gordon Child's learned book, "The Cultural Evolution of Man." Soon, adding the reading of other authors such as Graham Clark and Desmond Morris (the latter famous for his works "The Human Fauna" and "The Naked Ape"), it became clear that reading was not the fulfillment of a biological predisposition of the human species. Literacy, this process that leads us to think with admirable efficiency, is a powerful tool for enhancing the brain, a kind of neuronal application of extremely plastic causality far superior to the constraints of biological specialization; its most profound consequence is the possibility of deployment of abilities such as empathy and creativity starting from in-depth reading.

We evolve by means of the quality of our thinking, the quality of what we read and with in-depth reading that allows the humanity of others to shine through in ourselves. In-depth reading not only fosters a higher level of empathy, but also enriches our basal knowledge resource, expanding the freedoms of the mind and making it virtually more creative, critical, and receptive to insights. Although the lack of empathy among our young people is glaring, the psychological and emotional capacity to put oneself in another's shoes seems to have encountered ideal conditions to succumb to vanity and authoritarianism in academic environments. Interestingly, hives form (certainly not by empathy!) around rigid thinking aimed at shielding reactive groups from creative and disruptive "invaders." In these circles, in-depth reading is not very frequent outside the specific areas of teaching and research, which tends to harden minds against innovative proponents. Boyowald, in a critical warning stance, points out that "The formation of scientific alliances, whether public or secret, is certainly inconvenient, since they would easily pressure those who investigate individually." Further on, he continues: "From the point of view of research policy, any flourishing sector is interested in repressing the competence of alternative trends." Such admonitions, I believe, are justified because we see science taking paths that contradict what are expected to be two of its foundations: 1) independence from motivations other than its own *raison d'être*, and 2) the beneficial freedom of creative critical thinking. I have no doubt that a lack of empathy is an important component

in the current configuration of the academic world, for which creativity has become a dangerous thorn if it is out of fashion or outside the control of the prevailing group. Schopenhauer already outlined the context that would form the perfect setting for the flourishing of a lack of empathy: "[...] the strident scholastic rivalry of professorships and examining boards, whose internal driving forces are always made up of personal objectives [...]." Considering that academic discussions are far from showing any sign of in-depth reading of authors such as Tolstoy, Twain, Emerson, Saint-Exupéry, Machado de Assis, and so many others, I fear that academia, as it stands today, is not recommended for the development and preservation of the highest distinctions of human nature.

In compensation, neurosciences have made considerable progress in understanding how the human brain works, but not so much in understanding its mind. We are now far more aware of our ignorance than we were in the 1970s and 80s. Seminal works such as those by Chalmers (1995), Hofstadter (2007) and Smythies (2014), each with different approaches, and further contributions from Cicurel & Nicolelis (2015) and Penrose (2023), with emphasis on artificial intelligence (AI), have presented us with a new perspective on the complexity and scale of the challenges that await us. That being said, and focusing on cognitive neuroscience in particular, we still do not know for sure the real impact of the lack of in-depth reading on cognition in favor of the superficial and fragmented reading pattern of screens. What we already know for sure is the dispersive nature of digital environments, and how these environments hinder in-depth reading, conditioning the brain to shallow cognitive processes and to inattentive, quick, and disconnected reading. Importantly, people's growing impatience with longer readings that require greater intellectual effort is a strong indicator of a dangerous shift in the reading circuit.

The risks of a digital life for the reading circuit, so well described by Wolf (2019), are undeniably greater now with the arrival and indiscriminate use of generative AI. Cognitive offloading, that is, the outsourcing of cognitive tasks to computational algorithms, is a recurring fact, frequently masked by an excuse as shallow as the reading on a screen: saving time! If reading is done with the prior intention of saving time, the reasoning behind this behavior follows the utilitarian-shortsighted pattern typical of consumer society. This means that there is a mental adaptation underway in order to establish shortcuts to save time (and it remains the question as to what the purpose of this time saving is!). The strategy of taking shortcuts in the reading circuit is particularly virulent because it spreads to other circuits without people

realizing it, trivializing affection in interpersonal relationships, reducing human interactions to the handling of shortsighted and egocentric interests.

Saving time only makes sense if we are clear about the need to manage our time in life to achieve objective goals (including creative downtime and leisure!). If such goals do not exist, saving time is merely an empty excuse for doing absolutely nothing useful. This is worrying because the absence of goals seems to be the daily reality for our young people and a significant portion of young adults from more recent generations. The theory, which I am now defending with Professor Francisco Miranda, is that not only is the capacity for empathy affected by a lack of in-depth reading, but also the very ability to envision and define concrete goals for a healthy and productive life.

In short, I believe we must find ways to reclaim in-depth reading — primarily readings that encourage philosophical reflection — and, consequently, in-depth thought. This will not be achieved on digital screens, but through good physical books, where different neuronal groups are stimulated and alerted in response to the stimuli emanating from the letters, words, smells, and textures of the pages, in a broad and mysterious empathetic connection with authors and characters in whom we see ourselves reflected. Screens should remain what they are, i. e., physical interfaces through which we request algorithmic operations from machines to search for and process data and information useful for our purposes. They should not be transformed into poor supports for the exercise of the most edifying activities of humankind.

With affection,

Nilo Serpa.

1 Introduction

Why have physical books and in-depth reading disappeared from classrooms? There is a confluence of factors that have been discussed in previous works (SERPA & CATHCART, 2021; SERPA, 2025-a; 2025-b; 2025-c), so that, summarizing in a *causa finalis*, it is the lifestyle we choose that makes us more and more distanced from novels, essays and chronicles. We want to travel on cruises and buy all sorts of things online; “enjoy yourself without get hot under the collar!”, as if life were just one permanent party. The choice itself is everyone's right;

nothing against entertainment, which is obviously very necessary for mental health. The problem is what we are losing when that choice becomes so radical.

There is no doubt that literacy has enabled an unprecedented adaptation of the brain, and that in-depth reading is an indispensable nourishment for contemplation and the habit of thinking deeply. Deep thought is the foundation of philosophy, that discipline which Bojowald (2024) very aptly calls "the older sister of physics," the forgotten sister, even depreciated in many academic circles. Contemplation, in turn, is a state of inner calm: no analysis or criticism, only listening to the echoes of existence and eternity, followed by the wonder we experience before what the universe hides from us. Here is a true manifestation of deep thought. Imagine how many neuronal groups were activated to elaborate it and then turn it into written thought. Certainly, the deep thought circuit co-opted extensive brain areas via the cingulate cortex, with great participation from the area of affect, establishing connections at dizzying speeds, sweeping away memorized background knowledge like lights, sounds, aromas, and textures, building the emotional links that connect memories and trigger new feelings in a vibrant cascade of sensations that flood body and mind.

Literacy should help us think a little more as a species, but that has not happened, or at least not yet. On the contrary, we are more individualistic and seemingly less concerned about what we will leave to future generations. This finding brings us back to the objective of this article, which is to highlight the need to promote continued studies on the potential cognitive impairments resulting from the absence of in-depth reading in the daily lives of young people and adults, discussing what we can expect from our coexistence with algorithmic entities. The article emphasizes the loss of empathic abilities as a result of the absence of in-depth reading, criticizing the visible disconnection between education and its classical fundamentals.

2 Consciousness and brain circuits

No discussion about brain circuits, especially the reading circuit, can be conducted without considering, even indirectly, the nature of consciousness. Chalmers (2002) already clearly positioned himself on the perspective of a theory of consciousness:

Against reductionism, I will argue that the tools of neuroscience cannot provide a full account of conscious experience, although they have much to offer. Against mysterianism, I will hold that consciousness might be explained by a new kind of theory. The full details of such a theory are still out of reach, but careful reasoning and some educated inferences can reveal something of its general nature. For example, it will probably involve new fundamental laws, and the concept of information may play a central role. These faint glimmerings suggest that a theory of consciousness

may have startling consequences for our view of the universe and of ourselves. (CHALMERS, 2002, p. 92).

In 2020, Ukachoke presented his essentials for a theory of the mind, fostering some interesting insights, instigating us to move forward in the challenge of constructing a physical theory of consciousness. From a physical point of view, Serpa (2023) presented a beginning for the construction of such a theory in his work “*The time in cognitive neuroscience: For a physics of mind focused*”. In that proposal, time is a central variable of conscious processes. Without going into the details discussed in the aforementioned reference, why is time so important in conscious processes? Because all consciously activated brain circuits reveals the intrinsic transmission of causality of all brain command chains; brain circuits operate in the past → present → future temporal sequence of events in our universe (past = memory, present = action, future = prediction or prevision).

Impressively, Einstein's theory of relativity, by establishing that time and space are not only inseparable but merge as one and the same thing, today demonstrates a phenomenal reach beyond its origins. Matter and energy are composites of space-time: matter → more space than time; energy → more time than space. Similarly, we must understand the brain-mind relationship. To see conscious brain circuits, it is important to merge the concepts of mind and brain. Mind refers to the processes, the informational circuits of causality that translate into emotions and thoughts, constituting an intelligence based on the complex material system formed by highly sophisticated and adaptable cells and networks, a material system called brain. As stated by Serpa (2023), “[...] consciousness does not occur in time, it is predominantly time in its own course, with the neuronal architecture as the organism that registers this course through the apprehension of the external world by mental copies of facts in succession, a process known as perception.” Moreover, further on, he concludes: “[...] a conscious process is a copy-slice of the external world (predominantly “duration”) recorded in a neuronal structure (predominantly “extension”) through an opaque blend of duration and extension called “perception.”

Since we remembered relativity, understanding consciousness is like understanding the idea of continuity in general relativity. The universe is an expanding space-time *continuum*. To be continuous means to be uninterrupted in indefinitely small extensions, and, in the physics of space-time, what is uninterrupted is the expansion that defines it on indefinable scales. It seems contradictory, but, in the ultimate essence of the *continuum*, scale is a concept that is not defined. A scale is a fixed thought instrument for measuring things made up of parts. The

continuum does not consist of parts; it only expands by its own moving nature. So is consciousness: continuous, moving, without applicable scales, therefore inaccessible by rulers. As Goethe (1785) so aptly put it: "One cannot say that the infinite has parts. All limited existences are in the infinite, but they are not parts of the infinite; rather participate in the infinite." (Free translation by the authors).

Thus, conscious circuits form perceptions of the real world — especially the in-depth reading circuit —, perceptions that are not parts of consciousness (rather participate in consciousness) but rich in empathy and potential for insights. The great difficulty for common sense in assimilating something whose dominant nature is temporal is that our sensory references are spatial in large. Time does not present itself as something "touchable" by the senses, although we presume that everything exists while time is artificially marked by clocks. For common sense, time and space are distinct things. However, we do not need to imagine consciousness trying to spatialize it. It is enough to understand that we were not made to "touch" time.

To get an idea of the problems involved in the search for an understanding of consciousness, Chalmers commented on the hypothesis proposed by neurobiologists Francis Crick and Christof Koch, who suggested that consciousness may arise from certain oscillations in the cerebral cortex, believing that such oscillations could explain how different attributes of a perceived object, processed by different neuronal groups in different regions of the brain, are merged into a synchronized coherent whole. The problem, as Chalmers also pointed out, is that we do not know why, for example, such synchronicity always results in a specific visualization regardless of the amount of interaction between neuronal groups, not to mention the attributes of the objects that stand out most in each visualization. This is a question that evokes the search of how subjective experience rises from physical processes in the brain, the so-called "hard problem". This is a problem that leaves us agnostic with respect to a scientific solution. We will probably have to accept our inability to "touch" time.

3 Oblivion times

The brain needs constant challenge because its functions depend on stimuli and provocations that access memory, convene diverse neuronal groups, excite the regions that control the interactions between these groups (insula and cingulate cortex), and alert the distraction inhibition systems so that thoughts can be concentrated. After all that we have said,

memory is the most tangible expression of the predominantly temporal nature of consciousness. All our choices and decisions demand memory, whether long-term or short-term. In a given culture, long-term memories are transmitted from generation to generation and can become archetypes in the collective unconscious, constituting traditions and shaping behaviors.

That memory is being strongly affected by digital habits, this is a fact. However, nothing compares to Socrates' fear; we are increasingly less interested in memorizing things that we now entrust to cell phones and tablets. Indeed, there is nothing to complain about in freeing the brain from purely utilitarian information (with due concern for maintaining updated backups!). The problem is that we are transferring the very foundations of cognition to machines and their algorithms; that is, the mental effort toward understanding and the background knowledge without which it is impossible to confront information and establish critical thinking are being artificially offloaded to computers of all kinds. Now, background knowledge is sustained by memory; if there is no background knowledge, memory is reduced to the most trivial; reasoning stumbles and becomes clouded, words fail, communication becomes difficult and unproductive. In addition, the lack of background knowledge is the main reason for the difficulty in establishing a life plan with well-defined goals. It is the constant contrast between the external world and background knowledge that allows, through mental copy-slices of observed reality, the construction of analogies that will serve as starting points for the realization of desired objectives.

Digital culture promotes a shift in how memory and experience are processed. The speed of digital consumption and the reduction — or almost annihilation — of experience in daily life hinder the social cohesion that collective memory provides to the cultural and ethical values of a people. Importantly, the constitution of identities and memories through social digital networks transforms cultural heritage into something volatile, shaped by algorithmic conveniences and uncritical intentional posts, which hardly ever preserve the deep legacy of a culture; information is passed on without any critical scrutiny. Furthermore, there is clear evidence that electronically mediated communication alters fundamental emotional and empathic processes, configuring the so-called "empathy crisis," a part of the general cognitive decline.

Being realistic, we are living in an era of forgetfulness. Entire communities now have their histories shrouded in the fog of oblivion that thickens each year. Unlike the wise men of Amerindian cultures, who preserved and passed on the beliefs and practices of their ancestors,

in our time few want to know about the legacy of their grandparents and great-grandparents. In two generations, this legacy vanishes forever.

4 The real enemies of in-depth reading: Empathy in danger

The loss of empathy is one of the most serious signs of humanity's regression. Our most virtuous actions, as well as our feelings of tolerance and compassion, depend on the degree of empathy we manifest when interacting with other beings. In-depth reading strengthens empathy and general sensitivity to appreciate and better understand the world. Our greatest concerns lie in the fact that the quality of what we read and how we read no longer seem to constitute important matters for education. To a certain extent, like Socrates, perhaps we should ask ourselves what we are losing with the change in the reading brain.

Indeed, there is a similarity between Socrates' concern about the loss of the ability to memorize in face of increasing reliance on written language, and our concern on the current loss of cognitive ability in face of the growing appeal of digital devices and generative AI. We may have lost some of our highly developed memory when written records became established as an expression of a technology that was here to stay and would change the world forever. However, we have adapted and learned to make the most of both forms of memory — thoughtful memory and written memory —, a fact about which Socrates could not have predicted.

The similarity suggested above, however, ends when we compare the systems of human ecology in the two eras. In Socrates' time, human ecology was not subject to the overwhelming daily bombardment of distracting visual stimuli that we see today. The ease with which such stimuli succeed one another, blocking any intention of concentration, has no analogy in the past. One could say that television initiated the deterioration of the capacity for concentration, making the mind lazier for in-depth reading, but this belongs to the recent past of consumer society and technological civilization, less than a century ago. Despite inhibitory systems of continued distraction, which are better developed in young adults, offering the ability to eliminate distractions and maintain focus, the effort required to sustain attention has become considerably greater with the widespread use of digital devices.

4.1 Empathy in the Northeast of Brazil

Ironically, due to negligence by public authorities with respect to telecommunications and information technology infrastructure in general, the tenacious people from the Northeast of Brazil still resists the digital onslaught of the contemporary world. Empathy is already a typical and well-known gesture of that people. Amidst all the adversities that have plagued a history of suffering, such as drought, neglect due to the lack of public policies to improve life in communities, social inequalities, exclusion, and prejudice, Northeastern Brazilians overcome everything with a culture based on welcoming, solidarity, and caring for one another. In the Northeast, the gesture of offering a glass of water, a cup of coffee, a plate of food, or simply attentive listening, is commonly seen as something natural, almost instinctive. This everyday empathy does not arise from excess, but often from sharing what little there is, which makes it even more significant. The Northeastern way of being is born from ancestral roots, in collective thinking, practices that strengthen community ties, and in collective action.

In small towns of the Northeast, this lifestyle is even more evident. At dusk, it is common to see residents gathered on the sidewalks, sharing conversations, stories, and laughter. Relationships are close and personal; everyone knows each other by name, and local events, however simple, become reasons for gatherings, conversations, and moments of relaxation accompanied by a hot coffee. This routine, present in both urban and rural areas, reveals a way of life marked by simplicity, collectivity, and affective bonds. The daily life of the Northeasterner, therefore, is not defined solely by its material conditions, but mainly by the richness of human relationships and the community spirit that sustains life in the cities of origin.

Currently, empathy is at risk due to the emergence of technologies. Physical presence, conversation, all of this is being replaced by excessive access to screens, leaving aside what we value most: affective and interpersonal bonds. On the other hand, it is important to recognize that technology does not need to be, in itself, an enemy of empathy and in-depth reading. It can even be a powerful tool for solidarity mobilization, visibility for social causes, and bringing distant people closer together. The challenge lies in how we use it. It is necessary to cultivate a critical awareness that allows us to use digital resources without abandoning the humanity that is a characteristic of Northeastern people. Initiatives such as the "Workshops of the Future" project, proposed by the authors of the present article and currently underway, respond to the call for a humanization of educational practices supported by digital devices. This proposal aims to revive in-depth reading through poetry and the rich literature of Northeast Brazil, as recorded in classic media such as physical books and printed cordel literature.

In a nutshell, Northeastern empathy, built on proximity, attentive observation, and shared care, faces the challenge of remaining alive in a world increasingly mediated by screens. Preserving it requires collective effort: educating for the responsible use of technology, valuing face-to-face relationships, and reaffirming, in daily life, the importance of welcoming. More than ever, it is necessary to remember that no technological innovation replaces human warmth, genuine listening, and sincere gestures of care. Keeping this capacity for empathy alive is also an act of cultural resistance and an affirmation of what makes us profoundly human.

5 The return of reason

It's easy to abandon the habit of reading, since we are not biologically predisposed readers. It can be safely stated that, in light of the collapse of education, it is no mere coincidence the growing inability to show empathy coupled with an inability to engage in deep reading. It is not surprising that younger generations are losing empathy, given that disinterest in dense reading and cognitive impatience are direct consequences of the irresponsibility of educational institutions and, in truth, of many teachers who have consciously or unconsciously adhered to the utilitarian model of education, half-hidden by the marketing of pedagogical models of questionable effectiveness at best. Looking at the history of the 20th century, that collapse is associated with the proliferation of totalitarian regimes, the abundance of pedantic and empty writings of postmodernism, and the various forms of ideological indoctrination that have left gaps in the lines of intellectual succession in Latin America, Europe, Africa, and Asia. The optimistic vision of the *Belle Époque* left no trace with the two World Wars and the Cold War, while the confusion between science and technology gave way to politics intertwining in both.

The main measure to be taken is to restore the classic role of education, freeing it from the utilitarian vision and the postmodern ideologies and discourses that have trivialized it and that ignore the process of forming background knowledge so essential to the reading circuit and to in-depth thought. In this return to the core of education, technology has its place offering support tools, never as an end in itself, nor as a means of replacing human intellect. Let us give an example of the aggregating use of generative AI brought here by Serpa (2026).

A theoretical model was proposed for a certain problematic context in astrophysical cosmology. The model aims to describe the universe in its most essential nature using

mathematical resources that are unusual in this area. As it is an ontological explanatory construction that is difficult to empirically test at the current stage of technological development, the author proposed an analogy in transformation optics capable of producing practical simulations of what we would actually observe with the material and laboratory resources that we do not yet have. To verify the consistency and validity of the constructed analogy, the author created an AI agent simulating an absolutely impartial physicist who would comparatively analyze the model and the imitation, possibly suggesting additions to reinforce the analogy. Building the physicist's profile was laborious. To escape the current academic pattern, with its vices, prejudices, ideological biases, and hive thinking governed by interests unrelated to science, an extensive set of behavioral rules and a simulacrum of disruptive thinking were necessary. In the end, having submitted two separate texts, one with the proposed model and the other with the possible empirical analogy, both described in detail, it was possible to affirm that about 30% of the analysis provided by the agent was useful, mainly regarding clarifying additions that would reinforce the analogy, and regarding additional bibliographic suggestions (obviously verified by the author). In this sense, the agent functioned as a research partner free from subjective manifestations, not as an actor who constructed a new and disruptive theory. The author's intellectual effort and cognitive abilities were not only preserved, but also benefited from the intellectual construction of an artificial agent. Similar initiatives can be undertaken in any field of study, bringing real benefits to cognition and the quality of the work conducted.

6 Final remarks

Analyzing the reality of Brazilian education since the 1950s, we see that the widespread difficulty in articulating answers to questions that require more elaborate thinking is due to the fact that the circuit of in-depth reading has almost never been activated. What educators unfortunately fail to understand is that changing methodologies or adding technology to teaching will not solve the deficiency in the quality of thought, which is directly proportional to the deficiency in the quality of what is read and how it is read. Thus, we have two great enemies of in-depth reading: 1) mass-market digital media accompanied by generative AI, and 2) utilitarian education, which together lead to the reduction of teaching to the fallacy of preparing for the job market. No one is prepared for the job market while not prepared for life.

Our criticism of educators is primarily an invitation to logical reflection, and we make it as educators ourselves. While these professionals are concerned with applying the so-called "innovative" methodologies, which lack sufficient studies to prove their real effectiveness, they fail to understand that the teaching-learning process requires the collaboration of various neuronal groups and the activation of different brain circuits, both in teachers and their students; no methodology will achieve this without background knowledge, without working memory under selective intelligence to identify important concepts to be reiterated in order to integrate long-term memories, and, lastly, without language proficiency. All these factors conditioning a good education depend on the habit of dense reading.

When the subject involves cognition, a vast field of research opens up with several obscure sectors. Many years of study and experimentation are necessary to obtain any satisfactory result. This is why education is such a complex topic, as it touches upon various circles of neuroscientific knowledge. Therefore, it is recommended that pedagogues and educators in general delve into the main issues of cognitive neuroscience, and that they seek to validate their methodological initiatives with the scientific rigor that the subject requires. This must be done with great attention to appeals to technology.

We do not condemn technology for the dangers it presents, but we do warn about them. Human creation always has two sides, like the two wolves that inhabit the spirit, according to Native American wisdom, one inclined towards good, the other towards evil; the one that is fed wins. We must feed the good use of technology in the ways it enhances our gifts. If we do not use it to aggrandize ourselves, what will we gain from it? We are still in the early stages of investigating how the brain is changing in a digital life. There is clear evidence of behavioral changes, especially among young people, regarding cognition, and thus, a potentially harmful cascading effect on the ability to express empathy and process emotions can be inferred. We do not have enough information in the current scenario to discuss the irreversibility and permanence of the effects already observed. There is no going back to the pre-digital world, nor is that what we want. Just as we learned to deal constructively with written language, we will learn to deal with the language of screens. However, it will always be necessary to keep in mind that it is healthy cognition that warrants empathetic access to the world around us, and this cognition will only remain healthy if we are the good readers who preceded us in the 20th century. May today's educators be lucid enough to recognize this truth!

Acknowledgments

HUMANIDADES & TECNOLOGIA (FINOM) - ISSN: 1809-1628. vol. 65 – mai. /jul. 2026

Doi 10.5281/zenodo.20331796

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Professional Master's Program in Development and Peripheries at Santa Úrsula University for their always-present support and encouragement.

References

BOJOWALD, Martin. **Antes del big bang: Una historia completa del universo**. 4ª Edição. Madrid: Debolsillo, 2024.

CHALMERS, David. The puzzle of conscious experience. **Scientific American** 273(6): 80 - 86, 1995. Reprint, with new layout and painting by Magritte, available online at: <http://consc.net/papers/puzzle.pdf>.

CICUREL, Ronald; NICOLELIS, Miguel A. L. **O cérebro relativístico: Como ele funciona e por que ele não pode ser simulado por uma máquina de Turing**. 1ª Edição. São Paulo: Kios Press, 2015,

GOETHE, Johann Wolfgang von. **Ensaio científico**. 1ª Edição. São Paulo: Ad Verbum Editorial, 2012.

HOFSTADTER, Douglas. **I am a strange loop**. 1ª Edição. New York: Basic Books, 2007.

PENROSE, Roger. **A mente nova do imperador: Sobre computadores, mentes e as leis da física**. São Paulo: UNESP, 2023.

SERPA, Nilo; CATHCART, Richard. The last quitters: nobody's science and physics. **Latin - American Journal of Physics Education**, v. 15, p. 1315-1 – 1315-6, 2021.

SERPA, Nilo. The time in cognitive neuroscience: For a physics of mind focused. **Latin - American Journal of Physics Education**, v. 17, p. 2304-1-2304-14, 2023.

SERPA, Nilo. Essentials on advanced cognitive neuroscience: Mental health, modern education and distance learning. **Revista Brasileira de Pesquisa em Ciências da Saúde**, v. 11, p. 1-10, 2025-a.

SERPA, Nilo. Machine learning in astrophysical cosmology: Education beyond the dominion of Big Techs. **Latin - American Journal of Physics Education**, v. 19, p. 3308-1-3308-8, 2025-b.

SERPA, Nilo. Essai sur la connaissance partielle: Les problèmes du langage en science et les limites de la connaissance. **CALIBRE - Revista Brasileira de Engenharia e Física Aplicada**, v. 10, p. 23-55, 2025-c.

SERPA, Nilo. The expanding space-time: The flow of nothing. **CALIBRE - Revista Brasileira de Engenharia e Física Aplicada**, v. 11, suplemento março, p. 1-32, 2026.

SMYTHIES, John. The nature of consciousness and its relation to the brain. **Journal of Consciousness Studies**, v. 21, p. 183-202, 2014.

UKACHOKE, Chirapat. **The basic theory of the mind**. Bangkok: Charansanitwong Printing Co., 2020.

WOLF, Maryanne. **O cérebro no mundo digital**. São Paulo: Editora Contexto, 2019.